

The Growing Threat of Ransomware to Young Women

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1. Introduction

1.1. Abstract

Ransomware attacks can meaningfully harm young women because they are more active online and more deeply integrated with digital platforms. These attacks can cause far reaching consequences in terms of financial, psychological and social impact. Additionally, young people are considered to be more vulnerable to ransomware attacks than any other group of people, thereby requiring them to understand more about cybersecurity.

As such, this paper touches on ransomware infection vectors, the data privacy and implications of ransomware attacks, how other new and emerging technologies like AI and blockchain technology affects the effectiveness and spread of ransomware, the social, physical, psychological, and financial impact ransomware particularly has on young women, the technical and non-technical counter-measures to mitigate ransomware and finally, an analysis of future trends related to ransomware attacks.

While this paper primarily addresses the implications of young women, the insights and countermeasures discussed are valuable for all internet users and should be considered essential knowledge for anyone seeking to improve their online security.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to increase awareness of the delicate situation young women face online, with a special focus on ransomware attacks, so that adequate prevention measures could be put in place and proper cybersecurity measures could be implemented to protect this vulnerable group.

This paper also delves into the impact that future technologies might have on the spread and effectiveness of ransomware. Covering these areas can serve as an “early warning” for identifying the future problems internet users and young women might face online, which can help them be more prepared and ready when or if these threats emerge.

1.3. Limitations of the Study

As with most studies, this paper proves to have some limitations in terms of its scope and applicability that you should keep in mind. Some of these limitations include but are not limited to the following:

- A) While we aim to focus on young women in particular, it isn't possible and feasible to fully capture the diversity within this group, such as the intricate differences from a socioeconomic and cultural perspective.
- B) The datasets that we are working with in this study are based on the current data and trends at the time of writing and may not be entirely accurate at predicting future developments. Furthermore, the study relies on secondary data and existing research, which limits opportunities for new and novel findings.

- C) Although most of the countermeasures, tips and insights are universally applicable, some of the recommendations in this paper might be more suitable for some individuals depending on the context and their specific situation.
- D) This study prioritizes ransomware, which might leave other potent forms of malware like viruses, keyloggers and infostealers less explored.
- E) Cybersecurity threats evolve rapidly and exponentially. Therefore, the recommendations that we provide in this paper might become outdated or ineffective as time goes on.

1.4. Definitions of Key Terms

- **Infection Vectors:** Refers to the methods or ways through which ransomware or any other malware infects a system. Examples include phishing emails and malicious downloads.
- **Countermeasures:** Are defined as the strategies implemented and used to counter, mitigate or respond to a malicious attack. These can be classified as technical such as antivirus software or non-technical like user awareness and education.
- **Young Women:** For the purpose of this study, the term “young women” refers to females aged between 12 and 30 years old. Extending the range slightly from the typical 18-25 range used in the majority of studies makes sense as teenagers are more and more active online and are very susceptible to these kinds of attacks. Furthermore, women in their late 20s remain active online often for

professional, societal or personal purposes, making them attractive targets to malicious actors as they are perceived to have the necessary funds to be able to pay the ransom.

- **OPSEC:** OPSEC stands for Operational Security, a term derived from the United States Military. It involves identifying critical information and protecting it from unauthorized access.

2. What is Ransomware?

2.1. Definition

The Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA) defines ransomware as “an ever-evolving form of malware designed to encrypt files on a device, rendering any files and the systems that rely on them unusable.” This type of malware leverages legitimate encryption services on the target devices, which may be used to provide important security features like full disk encryption or TPM attestation, to lock users out of their own files, rendering them inaccessible without the key that the attackers have. The attackers usually request to be paid a certain amount of money in exchange for the key. They often leverage cryptocurrencies like Monero due to the anonymity and intractability of the payments. Failing to pay the ransom can lead to severe consequences including permanent data loss, exposure and leakage of sensitive information, or a prolonged inability to access the system. Some of the basic ransomware attacks may lock the system without harming the files while others fall into the category of cryptoviral extortion.

Ransomware is a significant cybersecurity threat, targeting individuals, businesses, companies and even governments. “The more individuals and business rely on technology, the more it becomes part of their lives and cannot be replaced. Cyber criminals realized this fact and increased the demand for higher ransom” (Alwashali, 2021). The complexity and spread of ransomware attacks is on the rise and is projected to keep increasing in the

years to come, which is why it's important to shed light on this important and emerging issue.

2.2. Types

Ransomware attacks are categorized into diverse types, each used for a specific purpose or to infect a specific target. The most prevalent and common types of ransomware include but are not limited to:

1. **Crypto Ransomware:** Encrypts the victims files and demands payment in exchange for the decryption key. This is the most common type of Ransomware. Attackers leverage the improvements in blockchain technology to receive payments anonymously, and the rise of AI to make their ransomware scripts even more potent. Some examples include the infamous WannaCry (2017) and CryptoLocker (2013).
2. **Locker Ransomware:** Unlike crypto ransomware which encrypts files present on the target device, locker ransomware (as the name implies) locks users out of their system entirely by fully encrypting the device's interface or important operating system modules. Payment is demanded in exchange for accessing the device through the decryption key. WinLock (2006), which displayed pornographic images until victims send a \$10 premium-rate SMS to receive an unlock code, is one of the first instances of locker ransomware spotted in the wild.

3. **Leakware:** involves threatening the victim with the release of sensitive personal information or media, such as inappropriate pictures, unless the ransom has been paid. AI has recently been employed as part of these attacks to search the infected device in hopes of finding the most sensitive content and upload it to the attackers. This allows attackers to gain the most leverage on their victims without having to employ fake threats or manually search infected devices. A well-known example of this type of ransomware is Maze Ransomware (2019), which some argue has been attributed the first big use of data exfiltration combined with ransomware.
4. **Scareware:** employs psychological pressure, with fake alerts or threats that claim to infect the operating system with ransomware and require payment. Such techniques are already getting more realistic, with AI's rise in availability and accuracy. Scareware can also disguise itself as leakware to hit the victim where it hurts the most. RansomwareFake (2016) is an example of scareware which would display a fake ransomware screen and try to trick victims into thinking they have already been infected with real ransomware.
5. **Ransomware-as-a-service (RaaS):** makes ransomware available to various attackers through service models. The developers typically take a percentage of the ransom payments. Can leverage the use of AI for large-scale custom attacks. REvil (2019) is one of the most notorious RaaS platforms, allowing cybercriminals with little technical background or knowledge to rent or

purchase ransomware to carry out attacks on their own targets. The REvil group, which operates the platform, takes a cut of the ransom payments in exchange for providing access to the ransomware toolkit and the infrastructure needed to carry out the attacks.

2.3. Common Tactics

Ransomware attackers employ different strategies to increase the likelihood that a target device gets infected. Some of these tactics include:

1. **Social Engineering:** involves manipulating, deceiving, or using psychological tactics to influence victims to take actions that can harm their security or help the attacker's motifs. A SIM Swapping attack is a notable example of social engineering: the attacker calls the victim's mobile carrier pretending to be them. Through the use of publicly gathered information and breached or stolen data, the attacker can pose as the victim and request a SIM card replacement, gaining control of the victim's cell phone number without them even knowing. Social engineering can be effectively used to increase the likelihood that a target executes the ransomware file. Through deception, trickery and manipulation, an attacker can make it easier for victims to fall for this attack.
2. **Payload Dropping:** is when an attacker delivers and executes a malicious program (payload) on the victim's machine without their knowledge. This is often used in ransomware and many other types of malware. A reverse shell

- script delivered via email is an example of payload dropping. The victim would open the email, while the script would be embedded in a media or a document that the victim loads on their computer, allowing the script to execute.
3. **Trojan Horses:** a trojan horse is a type of malware that disguises itself as legitimate software to trick users into installing it, allowing attackers to perform malicious attacks on the system. This is one of the most common delivery methods of ransomware, as users are more likely to blindly grant administrative privileges to legitimate looking programs if requested, which would give the attackers the ability to deploy ransomware on the system. These threats are especially common in unmoderated download websites and P2P file sharing services like torrents.
 4. **Watering Hole Attacks:** are a lesser-known delivery method but can be devastating if pulled off correctly. This attack involves compromising a website that is frequently visited by a lot or a specific group of people, allowing attackers to plant malware on the devices visiting the website. If ransomware was chosen as the malware of choice after successfully infiltrating the website, the effects would be devastating.

2.4. Historical Context

“In recent times, ransomware has become the most significant cyber-attack targeting individuals, enterprises, healthcare industries, and the Internet of Things (IoT).” (Chakkaravarthy. 2022).

Historically, ransomware attacks mirrored broader societal biases, exploiting vulnerabilities in people perceived as more emotionally impacted by the exposure of sensitive information. Young women increasingly fell victims to these attacks, especially around the 2010 era.

In general however, ransomware started appearing in the late 1980s, with the AIDS Trojan developed by Dr. Joseph Popp, and widely regarded as the first ever ransomware attack. This malware was delivered via floppy disks pretending to be AIDS research software (hence the name). Then started the 2000s era, with some of the first major developments in ransomware coming with it. Locker ransomware started to make its first appearance around 2006 along with scareware, particularly fake antivirus scams which started spreading around 2009.

The next decade also came with major developments for this type of malware, with Cryptolocker being a major milestone in 2010 due to its robust encryption and ability to spread really quickly. WannaCry, NotPetya and SamSam, which are all famous ransomware attacks, have spread in 2017 and 2018, infecting systems worldwide including businesses, hospitals, and even governments.

Today, ransomware is on the rise at an alarming rate, especially considering the surge in remote working due to the pandemic, the increase in ransomware gangs, and the quick but often insecure implementations of modern technological advancements.

“Ransomware attacks are taking advantage of the ongoing pandemics and attacking the

vulnerable systems in business, health sector, education, insurance, bank, and government sectors.” (Poudyal, 2020).

3. Technical Analysis of Ransomware Attacks

3.1. Infection Vectors

“Nowadays, connectivity, software, and data storing vulnerabilities are challenges yet to be overcome in the realm of cybersecurity and computers” (Payre, 2023).

Ransomware exploits a lot of attack vectors to gain access to target systems, with some of the most notable attack vectors being:

1. **Email Phishing Campaigns:** This is the most common type of attack vector that malicious actors often abuse to deliver ransomware to their victims.

Cybercriminals write tricky and meticulously crafted emails that aim to mimic organizations or trusted colleagues, to trick victims into downloading malicious software on their devices. These attacks have grown into large campaigns that aim to cause as much damage as possible for financial gain.
2. **RDP Vulnerabilities:** Remote Desktop Protocol is a proprietary network protocol to access and control the data and resources of a target system via the internet. If it's not properly secured, attackers can exploit it rather easily to gain access to the target system. Unpatched systems and weak credentials are some of the most abused points of entry in regards to exploiting RDP and systems in general.
3. **File Sharing Services:** can prove to be a weak point if files shared through these services are unmoderated and contain malware. Torrenting is well known to be

one of the easiest ways to spread malware in the wild. Alternative app stores or download websites have also been shown to have a higher percentage of malicious payloads compared to their legitimate counterparts.

4. **DNS Spoofing:** involves redirecting users to a malicious website that delivers the payload. This is done by switching the domain name service of the website the user is trying to access to the one that the attackers want to route that user to. If the malicious website is made to visually look and behave like the original intended legitimate website, and a victim is tricked into interacting with the malicious website instead, hackers can pose all kinds of nasty attacks and threats to the victim's machine.
5. **Email Spoofing:** Email spoofing simply involves an attacker forging and faking the sender's identity to make the email appear more legitimate. A basic example of this is receiving an email from e1onmusk@tesla.com instead of elonmusk@tesla.com. Attacks have been employing much more sophisticated tactics like obfuscation through HTML and email cloning to make their emails look authentic. Another example of spoofing might be an attacker drafting an email pretending to be from PayPal. To the user, a spoofed message looks normal and safe because most attacks use elements from the official website in order to enhance their chances of tricking their victims.
6. **SMB Vulnerabilities:** Server Message Block is a protocol used for file sharing across networks. It has been abused in attacks like WannaCry to quickly spread

ransomware across networks. Many types of vulnerabilities and zero days are chained and exploited in order to make the spread of the ransomware even more effective.

3.2. Encryption Techniques

Typical ransomware particularly relies on heavy encryption in order to lock victims out of their devices. Earlier ransomware used basic encryption methods which were often easy to crack. However, modern ransomware uses advanced cryptographic algorithms like RSA and AES-256, which are extremely and/or virtually impossible to crack with today's hardware.

In the case of ransomware, most attackers use **asymmetric encryption**, which consists of both public and private keys, to make sure that the ransomware can survive analysis as long as the **private key** remains secure.

Some advanced ransomware on the market uses hybrid encryption, which is a combination of both asymmetric and symmetric encryption to ensure that the decryption key is even more protected from monitoring attempts or loggers.

Attackers automatically generate unique keys for each of their victims to make sure that one victims' decryption key cannot unlock other victims' data. These keys are usually stored on remote servers, adding another layer of security for the attackers.

3.3. Payment Methods

Ransomware operations are closely tied to the dark web, as attackers use that to sell RaaS kits, stolen data, and decryption keys. The dark web, through the help of the Tor network, gives them an anonymous place to lander payments and offer technical support.

It is no surprise that cryptocurrency is the preferred payment method for cybercriminals, especially regarding ransomware, due to its decentralized nature and promised anonymity. Attackers will provide victims with some kind of manual or instructions to help them purchase Bitcoin and send it to them, which lowers the technical barriers for non-experts.

While Bitcoin is popular, Monero has been favored by more sophisticated ransomware groups in recent years. Monero is a cryptocurrency specifically designed to keep transactions private and anonymous. Unlike Bitcoin, which uses a public ledger to keep track of transactions, Monero transactions are quasi-impossible to trace. This makes it the ideal choice for attackers that aim to avoid detection.

After receiving the ransom, attackers often use cryptocurrency mixing services which are also known as “tumblers” to shuffle the transactions around multiple accounts and to combine the transactions across multiple instances, further obfuscating the source of the funds.

4. Young Women and Ransomware

4.1. Why Young Women?

According to this year's research posted by Danisha Hasan, winner of the Outstanding Emerging Leader in 2024, the number of cyberattacks targeting women has increased significantly, with a staggering 1 in 5 women falling victim to phishing scams.

Young women are increasingly vulnerable to ransomware attacks. Given that this generation spends a considerable amount of time on the internet attending classes, working remotely, and socializing, they are easy targets for hackers.

According to a study published by Anna Cartwright, Edward Cartwright, Lian Xue and Julio Hernandez-Castro titled "An investigation of individual willingness to pay ransomware", "women and younger age groups are significantly more willing to pay a ransom, as are those who store photos. There is a strong positive relationship between concern for data breach and WTP a ransom."

Through phishing, social engineering and data theft, these attackers take advantage of this demography, which leads to blackmail, violations of privacy and severe interferences with their real and digital lives. The cyber-attacks that affect young women usually involve blackmail and extortion, since the stolen data is regarded as sensitive. Hackers might threaten to share compromising materials that include photos, videos or messages.

These types of threats are more severe for young women because their reputations are more easily ruined. This emotional manipulation is one of the things that attackers rely on in order to force victims into paying the ransom. Attackers try to “twist the knife” in a way to make it more likely that the victims succumb due to the pressure they are under. The psychological impact of blackmail can be profound, as victims often feel trapped and vulnerable, unsure of how to respond.

Another reason hackers aim for young women is because these women are more active online hence, they are more likely to have their details, passwords or even personal items saved on their devices or profiles.

4.2. Blackmail and Extortion

Ransomware groups have been using blackmail, extortion and sextortion tactics to target young women online. These attacks are also known as double-extortion attacks because the victim is not only pressured to regain access to their data but to stop the attackers from posting it online as well.

These threats usually prove psychologically pressuring, especially on young women, because they might be more willing to comply with demands under pressure due to fears of reputational damage. Attackers will often claim that failure to pay will lead to the data being publicly exposed, or that missing the first payment deadline will lead to some form of escalation, like contacting specific individuals in the victim’s life. The fear of

public humiliation or a major career impact forces victims to comply with the demands, even if the ransom is substantial.

Sextortion is another type of extortion that targets intimate or explicit data and content. Attackers try to do whatever they can to access private messages, photos or videos. For young women, especially those active on social media and dating platforms, there is a higher risk as hackers and attackers can leverage this online presence and exploit it to gain access to sensitive data. Some of the ransomware variants are specifically designed for sextortion. Attackers claim to have accessed a victim's webcam, an insecure cloud backup, or even the victim's browsing history even if they haven't, to psychologically trick victims into compliance. Other types of ransomware lie dormant in the victim's devices, allowing attackers to capture screenshots or access camera feeds. Attackers can then remotely trigger the encryption script when they obtain the necessary amount of information to use as leverage.

This type of attack is extremely cruel, as it exploits the disproportionate stigma that young women endure when their private content is exposed. These women become terrified of the judgement of society, peers and employers, which drives them to comply with the attackers' requests for payment.

4.3. Data Privacy

Data privacy is a key overlapping topic to discuss in regard to ransomware and young women, as these attacks often disproportionately affect them due to their digital

presence and the potential pressure faced from society if a data leak occurs. The core of the problem lies in how data is collected and stored in the first place.

One of the ways a data privacy compromise can lead to getting infected with ransomware is from data breaches. For examples, breached databases from fitness or dating apps can be used to deliver highly personalized attacks, especially since women are the majority users of these platforms. These apps can hold a gigantic amount of data such as daily activity sleep patterns and biometric information.

Social media platforms like Instagram, Snapchat and TikTok can even make the problem worse by encouraging users to share even more detailed information about themselves including their location, relationship statuses, and other identifying information which can be brutally exploited by bad actors to decide the timing, effectiveness and means of their attacks. These details might individually seem harmless but when combined into a profile, they can create a pretty accurate picture of what a person is like: their lifestyles, routines, fears, likes and pressure points.

“Multiple cyberattacks have been reported in the medical literature, most of which describe the technical aspects of the cyberattacks or their impact on a single hospital service/department” (Benvamine Abbou, 2024). Women healthcare providers such as cosmetic clinics, fertility clinics or doctor’s assessments have been targeted by ransomware. Because these records are so sensitive, women feel like they have no choice but to pay to prevent their data being exposed. Ransomware attacks have a significant effect on emergency department workflow, acute care delivery, and the personal well-

being of health care providers. Preparedness for such incidents is limited, and many challenges are encountered during the acute and recovery phase of attacks. “Ransomware attacks have a significant effect on emergency department workflow, acute care delivery, and the personal well-being of health care providers”. “Preparedness for such incidents is limited, and many challenges are encountered during the acute and recovery phase of attacks.” (Boven, 2023).

As such, bad online OPSEC and data privacy breaches can pose another attack vector or can help amplify the strength and effectiveness of ransomware campaigns.

Victims of ransomware can often lose confidence in being able to keep their data private online. This can lead to further attacks being more effective as less and less measures are being taken by victims to protect their data due to their “hopeless state”.

5. Prevention and Mitigation

5.1. Backups Are Your Friend

Backups are copies of data stored separate from the original for recovery or tracing purposes. Backups are the most effective prevention against ransomware, as the encrypted data can be recovered from an earlier backup without having to interact with the attacker or try to decrypt the existing files. Restoring to an earlier state allows targeted systems to be cleaned up.

It is important to restore to the earliest backup that is NOT affected by ransomware. Malware scans and system checking are important to make sure ransomware isn't lying dormant in earlier backups.

Regular backups are highly encouraged, in order to keep the newer data in the recovery process without losing weeks or even months of work. It is important to follow the **3-2-1** rule as a basic practice for backups. This unofficial but recommended rule states that you should have at least **three (3)** copies of your data at any given time: the original data and at least two backups. Your backups should be stored on **two (2)** distinct types of media (e.g., a local hard drive and a USB drive), and at least **one (1)** copy should be off-site, either stored on the cloud or in a separate physical location.

This rule ensures redundancy and protection from various threats, making your backup strategy optimal and foolproof. You should also test and verify your backups from time to time, to make sure it all still works flawlessly.

5.2. For Average Users

For average users, we recommend enabling automatic updates to make sure that your operating system and other apps are all up to date. Updates contain patches that mitigate security vulnerabilities that might be used by attackers to activate ransomware.

You should also have respectable antivirus software running at all times with its latest definitions and threat updates. Set the threats database to automatically update itself if possible.

Avoid clicking on suspicious links, especially in emails, texts, messages from untrusted parties, or too good to be true scenarios.

Use user-friendly backup services to synchronize your data automatically to the cloud. Choose a trusted cloud provider that has end-to-end and at rest encryption, and that is preferably privacy-friendly to avoid abuse of your data for targeted advertising or to train AI models.

Use trusted browsers which offer built-in security features and can be hardened for privacy and security. Consider installing a reputable ad-blocker that focuses on security to improve your odds at catching malware before it even makes it do your devices. Don't overdo it with the extensions as these can also pose various security threats. A few simple yet effective ones will do the trick.

Use strict email filters in your email service of choice if it allows you to. This helps to prevent phishing emails as effectively as possible.

Enable any ransomware protection that built-in tools in your device offers. Trusted third-party vendors also offer specific ransomware protection modules that can be quite easily installed.

5.3. For Technical Users

Technical users can start implementing various techniques in order to protect themselves against ransomware. Firstly, it is important to implement network segmentation to separate critical systems and backup data. This ensures that ransomware which can spread via networks doesn't affect backups as well.

EDR solutions can prove greatly beneficial at monitoring and responding to suspicious behavior at endpoints including ransomware. These tools can be a powerful help with the early detection and prevention of ransomware attacks.

Use backups that support version control and snapshots. This is effective because it allows for multiple recovery points, which greatly help with file recovery after an attack.

If a NAS is part of your network, you can enable built-in ransomware protection in most of the major vendors' products. You can usually find it as a toggle within the NAS settings that should be enabled by default. NAS backups should also be isolated from the rest of the network, for the same reasons listed above.

Immutable backups are very important to make sure that in the event that ransomware tries to change or encrypt backup data, it remains constant and cannot be altered.

Sandboxing suspicious files through a virtual environment is also good practice, as that allows the potential threat to be contained in the sandboxed environment rather than infecting your main system.

Advanced firewall configurations with application whitelisting enabled can help block inbound and outbound connections, filtering out known ransomware domains. DNS filtering can be implemented to block known firewall domains. Application whitelisting can also allow only whitelisted applications to run on a system, mitigating the risks of malicious payloads.

5.4. For Young Women

Most young women manage their own social media pages. They should make sure that accounts are secured using MFA and a strong password. Using a separate email and username for each account can also help mitigate the impact of data breaches and targeted attacks.

Back up your personal data including photos, videos, documents, or anything else that you may deem valuable on your drives. These files are irreplaceable and are often a big target for attackers.

Young women should be aware of phishing tactics, especially when engaging with social media, emails, and untrusted messaging platforms. You should be cautious with clicking random links and allowing untrusted and unsigned programs to run on your PCs. Always verify the sender's email address before trusting a message.

When sharing files, avoid using unencrypted platforms, as these can make it easier for attackers to access and store your sensitive data.

Avoid sharing sensitive information online. What is shared can't be taken back or deleted. Be cautious with third-party apps that are connected to your social media accounts. Set your accounts to "private" to protect against crawlers, and data scraping.

6. Future Trends

6.1. AI in Ransomware

In the future, AI could be used to analyze network environments and choose which files or systems it should encrypt. This can make attacks harder to spot. AI could also be used to develop more adaptive and more resilient payloads that can evolve in response to countermeasures.

AI could be used to aid in obfuscation efforts. This is called adaptive or polymorphic ransomware. This type of ransomware can change its code dynamically in order to evade detection.

AI can massively help with phishing email drafting, as it can greatly personalize these emails and tailor them in a way that is very manipulative and targeted at the victim. This can be done by leveraging the same technology to analyze their public social media profile and the data breaches they are part of to craft extremely personal and believable messages.

AI could be used to generate realistic voice, video calls and deepfakes. This will allow attackers to deploy even more effective phishing campaigns, increasing the spread of ransomware.

Using AI, ransomware may be able to check for weaknesses in network defenses and move laterally throughout that network while exploiting these vulnerabilities. “One such emerging security threat is ransomware attacks on the cloud which threatens to hold

systems and data on cloud networks ransom with widespread damaging implications” (Bhattacharya, 2021).

AI could play a role in ransom negotiations as well, which would more effectively put pressure on the victim and increase the impact of the physiological manipulations that the victims are under.

6.2. Blockchain and Cryptocurrency in Ransomware

Smart contracts on blockchain platforms could be used by ransomware attackers in the future for automatic execution of ransom payments once the victim meets required conditions.

Ransomware gangs may employ multi-signature wallets to obfuscate payments and mitigate traceability by law enforcement. This requires multiple private keys to authorize transactions, which improves security for the attacker.

Blockchain technologies could be used to track encrypted files, making it easier for attackers to know if a victim has paid the ransom or not. They may update blockchain records to show when files have been “released” to the victim. Blockchain technology might facilitate the creation of decentralized C2 servers, since blockchain networks don’t rely on central servers. This could help attackers’ servers be more resilient to takedowns.

The emergence and increase in popularity in privacy coins like Monero might also drive the rates of ransomware attacks upwards, due to the private nature of the transactions.

6.3. Ransomware-as-a-Service

The amount of content on ransomware as a service, RaaS, is scarce in academic literature. The majority of the articles are focused on the analysis of prevention measures and detection techniques of ransomware.

RaaS is increasingly adopting subscription models. These models often include support and various updates, making it easier for cybercriminals to access and maintain throughout their infrastructure. RaaS platforms may offer features automating the deployment of attacks, which brings down the amount of human involvement needed.

RaaS providers may offer analytics dashboards that track attack progress, such as how much ransom has been paid, how many systems are infected, and which victims are most likely to pay.

7. Conclusion

7.1. Content

“In recent times, ransomware has become the most significant cyber-attack targeting individuals, enterprises, healthcare industries, and the Internet of Things (IoT).” (Sibi Chakkaravarthy, 2022).

Ransomware remains an escalating threat, with its effects magnified on younger groups and individuals. This demographic is increasingly targeted due to their significant online presence and susceptibility to tactics like blackmail and extortion. The nature of ransomware attacks has evolved drastically, with attackers utilizing advanced methods such as data exfiltration, AI-enhanced phishing, and Ransomware-as-a-Service to exploit their victims more efficiently.

As ransomware tactics advance, young women must be increasingly careful about their online security. It is important for them to implement robust cybersecurity measures, including regular backups, secure passwords, and caution while engaging with social media and online platforms. Furthermore, understanding the psychological tactics attackers use, like sextortion and emotional manipulation, is essential in mitigating the risks.

The rise of new technologies such as AI, blockchain, and cryptocurrency has only made ransomware more complex and harder to defend against, which implies the need for constant adaptation in current and future cybersecurity strategies. While some preventive

measures like the 3-2-1 backup rule and maintaining up-to-date software can reduce the impact of ransomware, the constant advancements in cyber threats and particularly in ransomware demands that individuals remain informed and proactive in the online jungle.

Ultimately, this paper highlights the importance of digital security, particularly for young women, who must be equipped with both technical knowledge and emotional awareness to protect themselves against ransomware.

7.2. Young Women, be Careful

Young women face a unique set of challenges when it comes to digital security. The rise of ransomware, blackmail, extortion, and sextortion has made them a prime target for cybercriminals.

The psychological pressure exerted by cybercriminals during these attacks can be overwhelming, making them more likely to comply with ransom demands.

To protect themselves, young women must adopt solid cybersecurity practices. This includes securing social media accounts with strong, unique passwords and enabling Multi-Factor Authentication to add an extra layer of defense. Being cautious about what personal information is shared online and where it is stored is also important.

Awareness of phishing tactics is another key defense. Young women should be especially careful of unsolicited emails, texts, or messages from unknown sources, as these could be attempts to trick them into downloading malicious files or revealing personal information.

It's also important for this demographic to understand the potential consequences of data breaches and how hackers can exploit their digital footprint. Simple precautions implemented correctly can significantly reduce the likelihood of falling victim to these attacks.

The impact of ransomware can be particularly devastating for young women, affecting not only their financial security but also their personal and emotional well-being. It is increasingly critical for young women to be aware of the risks and take the necessary steps to protect themselves.

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